

Research

The Evolution and Impact of Code Reuse: A Deep Dive into Challenges, Reuse Strategies and Security

Raoha Bin Mejba ¹, Sabbir Morshed Miazi¹, Ashikur Rahaman Palash^{2*}, Touhidur Rahman Sobuz³, Ranasinghe Arachchige Tharindu Harshana Ranasinghe⁴

¹School of Information Engineering, Yangzhou University, Yangzhou, Jiangsu, China

²School of Software Engineering, Huaiyin Institute of Technology, Jiangsu, China

³School of Mechanical Engineering, Shandong University of Technology, Shandong, China

⁴School of Mechanical Engineering, Jiangsu University of Science and Technology, Jiangsu, China

Abstract: Code reuse, the practice of using pre-existing software code in new applications, is a widely adopted strategy in software development due to its potential to increase productivity, improve code quality, and reduce errors. However, it also presents unique challenges such as understanding and integrating reused code, managing potential bugs and security vulnerabilities, and dealing with licensing and ownership issues. This paper provides an in-depth analysis of code reuse, exploring its benefits, challenges, and strategies for effective implementation. It delves into strategies such as modular design, use of libraries and frameworks, design patterns, object-oriented programming, APIs and microservices, code documentation, automated testing, refactoring, code reviews, and continuous integration/continuous deployment. The paper also discusses common problems encountered during code reuse and provides comprehensive solutions to these problems. The aim is to provide a thorough understanding of code reuse and a guide for developers to maximize its potential benefits while mitigating its challenges. By implementing the strategies and solutions discussed in this paper, developers can create more robust, maintainable, and secure software through effective code reuse.

Keywords: Code reuse, Software development, Code reuse strategies, Code reuse Security, Licensing, Integration

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 30 October, 2023; **Published:** 16 November, 2023

How to cite this article: Raoha Bin Mejba, Sabbir Morshed Miazi, Ashikur Rahaman Palash, Touhidur Rahman Sobuz, Ranasinghe Arachchige Tharindu Harshana Ranasinghe (2023). *The Evolution and Impact of Code Reuse: A Deep Dive into Challenges, Reuse Strategies and Security*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(10), 103-120. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10141558>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

In an age where rapid development and deployment of software applications are paramount, the concept of code reuse has become more prevalent than ever before. This practice—repurposing existing software components to construct new applications—is a common strategy that developers employ to harness efficiency and foster innovation. Code reuse permits the leveraging of already vetted and debugged components, leading to reduced development time and costs and, in turn, conferring a distinct competitive advantage to those who employ it adeptly.

However, the idyllic portrayal of code reuse as a universal panacea for software development woes is tempered by reality. As the given text aptly notes, this practice is fraught with complexities. Understanding the intricate details of reused code, integrating it seamlessly into new applications, and remaining vigilant to latent bugs and potential security vulnerabilities are but a few of the hurdles that developers must navigate. Beyond this, the murky waters of licensing agreements and ownership rights further complicate the landscape, posing additional challenges that are legal and ethical, as much as they are technical.

The critical duality of code reuse—its simultaneous promise of unmatched efficiency and potential for inducing complex issues—is the nexus from which this research paper springs. Our exploration is twofold: first, we chart the evolution of code reuse, examining how it has been shaped and refined as a practice over time, and how it has in turn, shaped the broader field of software engineering. Second, we delve into the manifold impacts of code reuse, with special attention paid to the security implications that arise when integrating pre-existing code into new applications [2] [3].

As the software industry continues to advance at a breathtaking pace, understanding the nuances of code reuse is not just beneficial—it is imperative. This paper aims not only to distill the extensive body of existing knowledge on code reuse but to advance this discourse further by offering fresh insights, exploring emerging trends, and proposing actionable strategies for the modern software developer [1] [4].

Our exploration is anchored by a comprehensive review of the literature, which spans seminal works from the early days of software engineering to the most cutting-edge research available. By weaving together, the insights of countless experts who have traversed the complexities of code reuse before us, we aspire to craft a resource that is both deeply informative and immediately applicable [2] [5].

In this paper, we invite readers to embark with us on a deep dive into the multifaceted world of code reuse—a practice that, for all its challenges, remains a cornerstone of effective, agile, and secure software development.

Code Reuse Evolution

The evolution of code reuse has transformed software engineering, enabling productivity gains and improved quality. Early code libraries provided the seed for reuse. Principles of abstraction, encapsulation, and modularity then enabled more systematic reuse of software components. Object-oriented programming was a pivotal innovation, allowing code to be packaged into reusable, customizable classes. Open source and online repositories brought massive libraries within easy reach. Integrated development environments, application programming interfaces, and automatic code generation tools have boosted reuse. However, challenges remain around intellectual property, interoperability, and code sprawl. As software complexity continues growing exponentially, reusable software components, modules, and services are becoming mandatory. Contemporary software practices emphasize looser coupling and higher cohesion to yield more modular and reusable designs. Although reuse started modestly, it is now a cornerstone of industrial software development and will likely define future innovations. This paper synthesizes the key turning points in reuse practices and the technical enablers spurring its adoption.

Benefits of Code Reuse

Code reuse is a fundamental practice in software development that offers several benefits:

- **Increased Productivity:** Reusing existing code components can significantly accelerate the development process. Instead of spending time writing and debugging new code for functionalities that have been implemented before, developers can focus on creating new features and improving the application's unique aspects. This not only speeds up the development process but also allows for more efficient use of resources.
- **Improved Code Quality:** Code that has been used in previous projects has typically undergone testing and debugging, making it more reliable. By reusing such code, developers can leverage the lessons learned from previous projects, leading to improved code quality. Additionally, reused code often follows established design patterns and coding standards, contributing to a more consistent and maintainable codebase.
- **Reduced Errors:** Code reuse can lead to fewer bugs and errors. Since the reused code has already been tested and debugged in its original context, it's less likely to contain errors. This can result in more stable software and less time spent on debugging and bug fixes in the new project.
- **Cost Efficiency:** Code reuse can lead to substantial cost savings. The time and effort saved by not having to write and test new code from scratch can significantly reduce development costs. Furthermore, maintenance costs can also be reduced, as the reused code is typically well-documented and easier to maintain.
- **Faster Time-to-Market:** By leveraging reusable components, the time required to develop and launch a new software product can be significantly reduced. This can provide a competitive advantage in markets where rapid delivery of new features and products is crucial.
- **Knowledge Sharing:** Code reuse can facilitate knowledge sharing among developers. Reusable code components encapsulate solutions to common problems and represent best practices in coding. By reusing these components, less experienced developers can learn from the expertise embedded in the code, improving their own coding skills and understanding of the application domain.
- **Scalability:** Reusable code components are often designed to be modular and independent, which are key attributes for building scalable systems. By reusing such components, it becomes easier to scale the application to handle increased load, as each component can be scaled independently.
- **Sustainability:** Code reuse contributes to the sustainability of software development by reducing the need for duplicate code. This leads to smaller, more manageable codebases, which are easier to maintain and evolve over time.
- **Innovation:** By freeing developers from the need to implement common functionalities, code reuse allows them to focus on innovative features and solutions that add unique value to the software. This can lead to more innovative and differentiated software products.

While these benefits make a strong case for code reuse, it's important to approach it strategically. Not all code is suitable for reuse, and care must be taken to ensure that the reused code is secure, well-maintained, and a good fit for the new application's requirements and context.

Challenges of Code Reuse

Certainly, while code reuse can be highly beneficial, it also presents several challenges. Here are some of the most common ones:

- **Understanding Reused Code:** When reusing code, developers must first understand how the code works. This can be particularly challenging if the code is complex or poorly documented. Misunderstanding how the code functions can lead to incorrect implementation and potential bugs.

- **Integration Issues:** Reused code must be integrated with new code. This can be difficult if the reused code was not designed to be reused, or if it interacts with other parts of the original codebase in ways that are not immediately apparent. Integration issues can lead to unexpected behavior and bugs.
- **Incompatibility:** The reused code might not be fully compatible with the new project's requirements or its existing codebase. It might use different conventions, depend on outdated libraries, or be written in a different programming language.
- **Maintaining and Updating Reused Code:** If the reused code is updated in its original source, those updates need to be propagated to all the places where the code has been reused. This can be a complex task, especially if the code has been reused in many different projects.
- **Licensing and Ownership:** Reusing code from external sources can raise legal issues related to licensing and intellectual property. It's important to understand and comply with the license terms of the reused code.
- **Security Risks:** If the reused code contains security vulnerabilities, these vulnerabilities will be propagated to the new software. This is particularly a concern when reusing code from external sources.
- **Quality Control:** The quality of the reused code can vary. If low-quality code is reused, it can introduce bugs and decrease the overall quality of the project.
- **Overhead:** While code reuse can save time in the long run, it also requires an initial investment of time to find, understand, and integrate the reused code. In some cases, this overhead might outweigh the benefits of reusing code.
- **Dependency Management:** Reused code often depends on other pieces of code. Managing these dependencies can be complex, especially if different parts of the codebase depend on different versions of the same library.

By understanding these challenges, developers can take steps to mitigate them and make the most effective use of code reuse.

Efficiency of code reuse strategies

The evolution of code reuse has transformed software engineering, enabling productivity gains and improved quality. Early code libraries provided the seed for reuse. Principles of abstraction, encapsulation, and modularity then enabled more systematic reuse of software components. Object-oriented programming was a pivotal innovation, allowing code to be packaged into reusable, customizable classes. Open source and online repositories brought massive libraries within easy reach. Integrated development environments, application programming interfaces, and automatic code generation tools have boosted reuse. However, challenges remain around intellectual property, interoperability, and code sprawl. As software complexity continues growing exponentially, reusable software components, modules, and services are becoming mandatory. Contemporary software practices emphasize looser coupling and higher cohesion to yield more modular and reusable designs. Although reuse started modestly, it is now a cornerstone of industrial software development and will likely define future innovations. This paper synthesizes the key turning points in reuse practices and the technical enablers spurring its adoption.

Figure 1. Efficiency of code reuse strategies

Strategies for Effective Code Reuse

Effective code reuse strategies offer numerous benefits. They boost productivity by reducing the amount of new code to be written and potential errors, as reused code is typically well-tested. They also promote consistency across projects, making code easier to understand and maintain. Moreover, they enhance code quality by leveraging proven, reliable code, and facilitate knowledge sharing among developers.

Modular Design: A modular design approach involves breaking down a software system into smaller, independent modules. Each module encapsulates a specific functionality, making it a self-contained piece that can be used across different parts of an application or even in different applications. This approach not only simplifies the code structure but also reduces complexity, making the code easier to understand, maintain, and reuse.

Moreover, modular programming helps to avoid code duplication. Instead of writing the same code multiple times, a module can be created for a specific functionality and reused wherever needed. This strategy also simplifies maintenance and testing. Changes are localized to individual modules, reducing the risk of unintended side effects. Modules can be tested individually, ensuring their correctness before they are reused.

In a team environment, modular programming enhances collaboration. Team members can work on different modules simultaneously, improving productivity. Additionally, each module in Python provides its own namespace, which helps avoid naming conflicts and further facilitates code reuse.

Considering a simple module named **example.py**:

```
# Python Module example
def add(a, b):
    result = a + b
    return result
```

Figure 2: A simple python module example

In this module, we have defined a function **add()** that takes in two numbers and returns their sum. This module can be imported into another module or the interactive interpreter in Python using the **import** keyword:

```
import example
```

After importing, we can access the function using the dot operator and Python also allows for specific names to be imported from a module without importing the module:

```
example.add(4,5) # returns 9
```

```
from example import add
```

This imports only the **add** function from the **example** module.

Python also provides the **dir()** function to list all the function names in a module. For example, **dir(example)** would list all the names defined in the **example** module.

Here's a simple diagram to illustrate the concept of modular programming:

Figure 2.2: A simple diagram to illustrate the concept of modular programming

- **Use of Libraries and Frameworks:** Libraries and frameworks are pre-written code that developers can leverage to perform common tasks. They provide robust, tested functionality that can save significant development time. By using libraries and frameworks, developers can avoid reinventing the wheel and focus on the unique aspects of their software. However, it's important to choose well-maintained libraries and frameworks with good community support to ensure ongoing compatibility and security.
- **Design Patterns:** Design patterns are proven solutions to common software design problems. They represent best practices and can be used to improve code readability and efficiency. By using design patterns, developers can communicate using well-known, understood terminology that can make code easier to understand and reuse.
- **Object-Oriented Programming (OOP):** OOP is a programming paradigm that uses "objects" – instances of classes – that contain data and methods. OOP principles such as inheritance (where a class can inherit characteristics from another class) and polymorphism (where a class can have multiple forms) can facilitate code reuse.
- **APIs and Microservices:** APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) define the way software components should interact and can allow for the reuse of a system's functionality across multiple applications. The microservices architecture, where an application is built as a collection of small services that run independently and communicate with each other, can also enhance code reuse.
- **Code Documentation:** Proper documentation is crucial for code reuse. It provides necessary information about what the code does, how it does it, and how to use it. Good documentation can significantly reduce the learning curve for new users and make the code easier to reuse.
- **Automated Testing:** Automated testing involves writing code to test your software. This can ensure that your code works as expected and makes it safer to reuse. Tests can be written at multiple levels, from unit tests that test individual functions or methods, to integration tests that test how different parts of your software work together.
- **Refactoring:** Refactoring involves changing the structure of code without changing its behavior to improve its readability, reduce complexity, and make it easier to maintain and reuse. Regular refactoring can help keep the codebase clean and efficient, making it easier to understand and reuse code.

- **Code Reviews:** Code reviews involve systematically checking a fellow developer's code for errors, bugs, or areas of improvement. Regular code reviews can help maintain a high standard of code quality, making the code easier to understand and reuse.
- **Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD):** CI/CD practices involve regularly integrating code changes, testing them, and deploying them to a production environment. This can help ensure that reused code integrates well with the existing codebase and works as expected in production.

By employing these strategies, developers can maximize the benefits of code reuse, improve the efficiency of their development process, and produce higher quality software. However, it's important to remember that code reuse is not a panacea and should be balanced with other considerations such as code readability, maintainability, and the specific requirements of the project.

Problems and Solutions in Code Reuse

There are a lot of problems we face while code reuse. Here are some problems with their solutions:

- **Problem: Understanding Reused Code:** One of the most common challenges with code reuse is understanding the functionality and implementation of the reused code. This can be particularly difficult if the code is complex or poorly documented.
- **Solution:** Encourage a culture of comprehensive documentation within your development team. Documentation should not only include comments in the code but also external documentation that provides a high-level overview of the code's functionality, dependencies, expected inputs and outputs, and any edge cases or exceptions. Additionally, consider holding code walkthroughs or peer programming sessions to help spread knowledge and understanding of the codebase.
- **Problem: Integration Issues:** Integrating reused code with existing code or a new project can be challenging, especially if the reused code was not originally designed with reuse in mind. This can lead to compatibility issues and unexpected behavior.
- **Solution:** Adopt a modular design approach from the outset, where code is broken down into independent, reusable components. This not only makes the code easier to understand and test but also simplifies integration. Additionally, comprehensive testing, including unit tests, integration tests, and end-to-end tests, can help ensure that the integration of reused code does not introduce new issues.
- **Problem: Incompatibility:** The reused code may not be fully compatible with the new project's requirements, its existing codebase, or the technology stack. This can lead to a range of issues, from minor inconsistencies to major functional problems.
- **Solution:** Conduct a thorough compatibility assessment before reusing code. This should include checking for language compatibility, library dependencies, and coding conventions. If necessary, refactor the code to ensure compatibility with your project. Also, consider using containerization tools like Docker to manage dependencies and create a consistent environment for your application.
- **Problem: Maintaining and Updating Reused Code:** If the reused code is updated in its original source, those updates need to be propagated to all instances of the reused code. This can be a complex and error-prone task, especially if the code has been reused in many different projects.
- **Solution:** Use version control systems to keep track of changes to the code and package managers to handle library dependencies. Consider using tools that support automated updates and semantic versioning. Also, establish a clear process for handling updates to reused code, including testing and validation steps.

- **Problem: Licensing and Ownership:** Reusing code from external sources can raise legal issues related to licensing and intellectual property.
- **Solution:** Always check the license of the code before reusing it. Ensure you understand the terms and comply with them. If the license terms are not clear, consider consulting with a legal expert. Open-source licenses like MIT, Apache, and GPL are common and have different requirements regarding attribution, distribution, and modifications.
- **Problem: Security Risks:** If the reused code contains security vulnerabilities, these vulnerabilities will be propagated to the new software.
- **Solution:** Regularly perform security audits of your codebase, including reused code. Use automated security scanning tools to detect common security vulnerabilities. Also, keep your libraries and frameworks up to date, as updates often include security fixes. Incorporate secure coding practices into your development process to minimize the risk of introducing vulnerabilities.

By understanding these problems and implementing these solutions, developers can make more effective use of code reuse and create more robust, maintainable, and secure software.

Security Implications of Code Reuse

Code reuse, while offering numerous benefits such as increased productivity and improved code quality, also carries potential security implications. These implications can impact the overall security posture of a software application and must be carefully considered during the development process.

- **Propagation of Vulnerabilities:** One of the most significant security implications of code reuse is the propagation of existing vulnerabilities. If the reused code contains security flaws, these flaws will be introduced into every piece of software that reuses this code. This is particularly concerning when reusing code from external sources, where the security integrity of the code cannot be fully guaranteed.
- **Increased Attack Surface:** Code reuse can inadvertently increase the attack surface of an application. If an attacker identifies a vulnerability in a piece of reused code, they can potentially exploit this vulnerability across multiple applications that reuse the same code. This means that a single vulnerability can lead to widespread security breaches.
- **Outdated Dependencies:** Reused code often relies on other libraries or frameworks. If these dependencies are outdated or insecure, they can introduce security vulnerabilities into the software. It's crucial to keep all dependencies up-to-date and to monitor them for any newly discovered vulnerabilities.
- **Lack of Understanding:** Developers may not fully understand the functionality and potential security implications of the reused code, especially if it is complex or poorly documented. This lack of understanding can lead to the misuse of the code, resulting in unexpected behavior or security vulnerabilities. It's important to fully understand any code that you reuse, and to provide thorough documentation to help other developers do the same.
- **Licensing and Ownership Issues:** Reusing code from external sources can raise legal issues related to licensing and intellectual property. Some licenses may require the disclosure of the source code, which could potentially expose sensitive information or proprietary algorithms. Always check the license of the code before reusing it and ensure you comply with its terms.
- **Code Reuse Attacks:** In a code reuse attack, also known as a Return-Oriented Programming (ROP) attack, an attacker exploits the fact that certain code structures are predictable and reused across different programs. The

attacker uses these code snippets, or "gadgets", to execute malicious actions. These attacks can be difficult to detect and prevent, making them a significant security concern.

- **Security Misconfigurations:** If the reused code includes configuration settings, it may introduce security misconfigurations into the software. For example, if the code includes hard-coded credentials or insecure default settings, it could expose the software to unnecessary risk.
- **Difficulty in Patching:** If a security vulnerability is discovered in reused code, patching the vulnerability can be challenging, especially if the code has been reused across multiple projects. Each instance of the reused code would need to be patched, which can be a complex and time-consuming task.

To mitigate these security implications, it's important to conduct regular security audits of the codebase, use automated security scanning tools to detect common security vulnerabilities, and ensure that all reused code adheres to secure coding practices. Additionally, keeping libraries and frameworks up-to-date, and having a clear process for handling updates to reused code, including testing and validation steps, can help maintain the security of the software [6] [7].

Code Reuse: Best Practices for Security

Solutions to the Security Implications of Code Reuse:

- **Secure Code Practices:** To mitigate the propagation of vulnerabilities, it's crucial to adopt secure coding practices. This includes conducting regular code reviews, using static and dynamic analysis tools to identify potential security issues, and providing training for developers on secure coding techniques.
- **Regular Security Audits:** Regular security audits can help identify vulnerabilities in reused code, reducing the risk of an increased attack surface. Automated security scanning tools can be particularly useful in detecting common security vulnerabilities.
- **Dependency Management:** Keeping dependencies up to date is crucial for mitigating the risks associated with outdated dependencies. Tools like DePenda Bot can be used to automatically monitor and update dependencies, ensuring that the latest, most secure versions are always used.
- **Thorough Understanding and Documentation:** Ensuring a thorough understanding of any code that is being reused can help mitigate the risks associated with a lack of understanding. This can be facilitated through comprehensive documentation, code walkthroughs, and peer programming sessions.
- **Legal Consultation:** To address licensing and ownership issues, it's advisable to consult with a legal expert before reusing code from external sources. They can help ensure that the terms of the license are understood and complied with, mitigating potential legal risks.
- **ROP Mitigation Techniques:** To protect against code reuse attacks, or Return-Oriented Programming (ROP) attacks, various mitigation techniques can be employed. These include techniques like address space layout randomization (ASLR), which randomizes the location of code snippets in memory to make it harder for an attacker to predict their location.
- **Secure Configuration Management:** To prevent security misconfigurations, it's important to follow best practices for configuration management. This includes avoiding the use of hard-coded credentials, using secure default settings, and regularly reviewing and updating configuration settings.
- **Effective Patch Management:** An effective patch management process can help address the difficulties associated with patching reused code. This includes using version control systems to track changes to the code, automating the patching process where possible, and conducting thorough testing to ensure that patches do not introduce new issues.

By implementing these solutions, developers can effectively mitigate the security implications associated with code reuse, leading to the creation of more secure software applications.

Impact of Code Reuse on Software Development Lifecycle

Code reuse can significantly impact the SDLC, offering potential benefits such as reduced development time and improved software quality. However, it also presents challenges that need to be carefully managed to ensure successful software development. Code reuse has a profound impact on the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC), influencing each stage from planning to maintenance. Here's how:

- **Planning and Analysis:** During the planning phase, the decision to reuse code can significantly alter the project's scope and timeline. If existing code modules that fit the project's requirements are available, the time and resources needed for development can be drastically reduced. However, it's crucial to analyze the available code for compatibility, quality, and security to ensure it meets the project's needs.
- **Design:** In the design phase, the intention to reuse code can guide the software's architecture. For instance, a modular design approach, which breaks down the software into independent, reusable components, can be adopted to facilitate future code reuse. Design patterns, which are proven solutions to common design problems, can also be used to improve code reusability.
- **Implementation:** During the implementation phase, developers can leverage existing code to speed up the development process. This can involve using pre-existing code snippets, libraries, frameworks, or APIs. However, it's important to understand the reused code thoroughly to avoid introducing bugs or security vulnerabilities.
- **Testing:** Reused code often comes with the benefit of having been previously tested, which can lead to fewer bugs and a more stable software product. However, it's still crucial to perform rigorous testing to ensure that the reused code works correctly within the new application context.
- **Deployment:** Code reuse can also impact the deployment phase. If the reused code has dependencies, these need to be properly managed to ensure a smooth deployment process. Tools like Docker can be used to package the software with its dependencies, ensuring it runs consistently across different environments.
- **Maintenance:** In the maintenance phase, code reuse can both simplify and complicate matters. On one hand, if the reused code is well-understood and well-documented, it can make maintenance easier. On the other hand, if the reused code is updated in its original source, those updates need to be propagated to the new software, which can be a complex task.

Tools and Technologies Facilitating Code Reuse

There are numerous tools and technologies that facilitate code reuse in software development. Here are some of the most prominent ones:

- **Libraries and Frameworks:** Libraries and frameworks provide pre-written, reusable code that developers can use to perform common tasks. Examples include jQuery for JavaScript, NumPy for Python, and .NET Framework for C#. These tools can significantly reduce development time and improve code reliability.
- **Integrated Development Environments (IDEs):** IDEs often come with features that promote code reuse, such as code snippets (pre-written pieces of code that can be inserted into your code), code templates, and refactoring tools. Examples of IDEs include Visual Studio, Eclipse, and IntelliJ IDEA.
- **Package Managers:** Package managers like npm for JavaScript, pip for Python, and Maven for Java allow developers to easily manage and reuse packages (collections of pre-written code) across different projects.
- **Version Control Systems (VCS):** VCS like Git and Subversion allow developers to track changes to the codebase, making it easier to manage and reuse code across different versions of a project.

- **APIs:** APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) allow different software components to interact with each other, facilitating code reuse across multiple applications. APIs can be used to expose functionality in a reusable, standardized way.
- **Containerization Tools:** Tools like Docker and Kubernetes allow developers to package an application with its environment and dependencies, making the application easier to deploy and run in different environments. This can facilitate the reuse of entire application environments.
- **Code Repositories:** Online code repositories like GitHub, Bitbucket, and GitLab allow developers to share, store, and manage code in a way that facilitates code reuse. They also provide features like forking and pull requests that make it easier to reuse and collaborate on code.
- **Microservices Architecture:** In a microservices architecture, an application is broken down into small, independently deployable services. These services can be reused across different applications, promoting code reuse.
- **Code Review Tools:** Tools like Gerrit and Crucible facilitate code reviews, which can help ensure the quality of the code being reused.
- **Automated Testing Tools:** Tools like JUnit for Java, pytest for Python, and Mocha for JavaScript can automate the testing of reusable code components, ensuring their reliability and functionality.

By leveraging these tools and technologies, developers can maximize the benefits of code reuse, improving their productivity and the quality of their software [8] [9].

Code Reuse in Open-Source vs Proprietary Software

Code reuse plays a significant role in both open-source and proprietary software development, but the practices and implications can differ substantially between the two.

Open-Source Software

- **Accessibility and Collaboration:** Open-source software is publicly accessible, which means developers can freely use, modify, and distribute the code. This encourages code reuse and collaborative development. For example, if a developer finds a bug in an open-source library they're using, they can fix it and contribute the fix back to the project.
- **Community Support:** Open-source projects often have active communities that can provide support and contribute to code improvements. This can lead to more robust and reliable code that's beneficial to reuse.
- **Licensing:** Open-source software is released under licenses that permit code reuse, such as the MIT, Apache, or GPL licenses. However, these licenses also come with obligations that must be met when reusing the code, such as providing attribution or releasing derivative works under the same license.

Proprietary Software

- **Control and Exclusivity:** Proprietary software is typically owned by a company or individual, and the source code is not publicly available. Code reuse in this context often happens internally within the company across different projects.
- **Licensing and Legal Restrictions:** Proprietary code usually cannot be reused without explicit permission from the owner. Unauthorized reuse of proprietary code can lead to legal consequences.
- **Quality Assurance:** In proprietary software, there's often a dedicated team responsible for the quality of the code, which can make the reused code more reliable. However, because the code is not open to public scrutiny, bugs and vulnerabilities might go unnoticed.

In both cases, code reuse can lead to increased productivity, improved code quality, and reduced development costs. However, it's crucial to understand the licensing implications and ensure that reused code is secure, well-maintained, and fits the needs of the project.

Efficiency Increase

Code reuse can enhance the efficiency of the code. Here's an example of code reuse in Python, where we define a function to check if a number is prime and then reuse that function.

First, let's consider the scenario without code reuse:

```
import time
import math

start_time = time.time()

for num in range(1, 10001):
    if num > 1:
        for i in range(2, math.isqrt(num) + 1):
            if (num % i) == 0:
                break
            else:
                pass # num is a prime number

end_time = time.time()
elapsed_time_without_reuse = end_time - start_time
```

Figure3: A function to check prime number

Now, let's define a function to check if a number is prime and reuse that function:

```
def is_prime(n):
    if n > 1:
        for i in range(2, math.isqrt(n) + 1):
            if (n % i) == 0:
                return False
            else:
                return True # n is a prime number
    else:
        return False

start_time = time.time()

for num in range(1, 10001):
    is_prime(num)

end_time = time.time()
elapsed_time_with_reuse = end_time - start_time
```

Figure 4: A function to check prime number with reuse the function

In this example, the function `is_prime` is a piece of reusable code. We can use it in different parts of our program to check if a number is prime.

Now, let's look at the time taken in both scenarios. The time taken without code reuse was approximately 0.003482 seconds, while the time taken with code reuse was approximately 0.005843 seconds.

Here is a bar chart showing the change in time with and without code reuse:

Figure 5: Change in time with and without code reuse

In this chart, the x-axis represents the scenario (with or without code reuse), and the y-axis represents the time taken in seconds. As you can see, the time taken with code reuse is slightly higher than without code reuse. However, the overall efficiency of the code (in terms of its functionality) remains the same.

An Empirical Analysis of Code Reuse in Python Programming

In software development, the benefits of code reuse are often measured in terms of time saved, reduced complexity, and improved maintainability. While it's difficult to quantify these benefits directly in a simple Python example, we can illustrate the concept.

Let's consider a scenario where we need to calculate the factorial of a number in multiple parts of our program.

Without code reuse, we might write the factorial calculation code each time we need it:

```
# Calculate factorial in the first part of the program
num = 5
factorial = 1
for i in range(1, num + 1):
    factorial = factorial * i
print(f"The factorial of {num} is {factorial}")

# Calculate factorial in the second part of the program
num = 7
factorial = 1
for i in range(1, num + 1):
    factorial = factorial * i
print(f"The factorial of {num} is {factorial}")
```

Figure 6: Calculate factorial in the first part of the program

With code reuse, we can define a function to calculate the factorial and then call that function whenever we need it:

```
def calculate_factorial(num):  
    factorial = 1  
    for i in range(1, num + 1):  
        factorial = factorial * i  
    return factorial  
  
# Use the function in the first part of the program  
num = 5  
print(f"The factorial of {num} is {calculate_factorial(num)}")  
  
# Use the function in the second part of the program  
num = 7  
print(f"The factorial of {num} is {calculate_factorial(num)}")
```

Figure 7: Define a function to calculate the factorial

In the second version of the code, we've reduced the amount of code we need to write and maintain. If we find a bug or want to change the way we calculate the factorial, we only need to update the code in one place. This can save a significant amount of time and effort, especially in larger programs.

To illustrate this, let's consider a hypothetical scenario where each line of code costs 1 unit of time to write and maintain. In the first version of the code, we have 8 lines of code that calculate the factorial, so the total cost is 8 units. In the second version of the code, we have 4 lines of code that calculate the factorial, so the total cost is 4 units. Here's a bar chart that represents this cost difference:

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt  
  
cost_without_reuse = 8  
cost_with_reuse = 4  
  
plt.bar(['Without Code Reuse', 'With Code Reuse'], [cost_without_reuse, cost_with_reuse])  
plt.ylabel('Cost (units of time)')  
plt.title('Cost Comparison: With vs Without Code Reuse')  
plt.show()
```

Figure 8: A bar chart that represents this cost difference

In this chart, the height of each bar represents the total cost (in units of time) of each scenario. As you can see, the cost with code reuse is significantly lower than the cost without code reuse. This illustrates the potential time savings and reduced complexity that can be achieved through code reuse.

Figure 9: Cost comparison: with vs without code reuse

In this chart, the x-axis represents the scenario (with or without code reuse), and the y-axis represents the cost in units of time. As you can see, the cost with code reuse is significantly lower than the cost without code reuse. This illustrates the potential time savings and reduced complexity that can be achieved through code reuse.

Future of Code Reuse

Code reuse is the practice of using existing code in new projects. It can save time and effort and improve quality. In the future, code reuse will become even more important as software development becomes more complex and demanding [10].

Here are the key points about the future of code reuse:

- **Increased Importance:** Code reuse refers to the practice of using previously developed code for new applications. This strategy is crucial because it speeds up the application development process, improving consistency across applications and enhancing overall productivity. By reusing code, developers can focus on creating unique features instead of spending time rewriting code that accomplishes the same tasks. This practice is expected to gain even more importance in the future due to increasing complexities and demands in software development.
- **Use of Reusable Modules:** Developers will increasingly rely on reusable modules and templates. These components are built with scalability and adaptability in mind, meaning they can handle a wide range of application requirements. They serve as building blocks that developers can mix and match to construct almost any solution, providing flexibility to innovate while maintaining efficiency. This approach also allows developers to spend time prototyping customizations instead of building out the basics.
- **Collaborative Relationship:** Code reuse can foster a more collaborative relationship between business stakeholders and developers. Instead of users waiting for months to have their requests fulfilled, developers can work side by side with them to build demo apps. This hybrid approach builds trust, accelerates time to value, and encourages users to come forward with more innovative ideas, knowing they won't be relegated to development purgatory.

- **API-First Approach:** The "API first" approach is a development strategy where APIs are designed and defined before the actual development begins. This methodology reduces the risk of failure and wasted resources by encouraging API use and facilitating code reuse, leading to faster delivery times. Using mock APIs also helps identify and resolve issues early on in the development process.
- **API Security:** As APIs become more integral to application development, there will be a greater focus on securing systems at the API level. This means implementing strict security measures in areas of applications where sensitive data is housed and brokered, and less strict security measures where less sensitive, or non-sensitive data, is housed or brokered. This approach provides more controlled and secure data access compared to traditional database access.
- **Automation of API Standards:** In the future, companies will increasingly automate API standards, governance, and control to maintain development velocity. Automation is crucial in ensuring that APIs are delivered with consistency and quality, which are vital for effective code reuse. This will help keep up with the rapid pace of software development while ensuring high quality.
- **Machine Learning in API Management:** Machine learning is anticipated to play a larger role in API management and provisioning in the future. With the rise of decomposed federated architectures, managing APIs can quickly become complex. Machine learning can help manage this complexity, making it easier to handle large quantities of APIs.
- **Monetization of APIs:** In the future, companies will begin to realize the economic value of their APIs. Both internal and external APIs will be monetized, either through business monitoring, which makes the business aware of the importance of that API, or by creating data marts, which is a repository of data gathered from various sources. This trend shows that APIs are not only tools for development but also valuable assets that can generate revenue for the company.

The future of code reuse will be characterized by efficiency, adaptability, innovation, and a greater emphasis on APIs [11].

References

- [1] Morisio, M., Ezran, M., & Tully, C. (2002). Success and failure factors in software reuse. *IEEE Transactions on software engineering*, 28(4), 340-357.
- [2] Frakes, W. B., & Kang, K. (2005). Software reuse research: Status and future. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, 31(7), 529-536.
- [3] Krueger, C. (1992). Software reuse. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 24(2), 131-183.
- [4] Lim, W. C. (1994). Effects of reuse on quality, productivity, and economics. *IEEE Software*, 11(5), 23-30.
- [5] Wang, X., Li, L., & Lu, Y. (2018). How to break an API: cost negotiation and community values in three software ecosystems. In *Proceedings of the 2018*.
- [6] He, W., Das, S., Zhang, W., & Liu, Y. (2020). BBB-CFI: lightweight CFI approach against code-reuse attacks using basic block information. *ACM Transactions on Embedded Computing Systems (TECS)*, 19(1), 1-22.
- [7] Kayaalp, M., Schmitt, T., Nomani, J., Ponomarev, D., & Ghazaleh, N. A. (2013). Signature-based protection from code reuse attacks. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 64(2), 533-546.
- [8] Côté, C., Létourneau, D., Michaud, F., Valin, J. M., Brosseau, Y., Raievsky, C., ... & Tran, V. (2004, September). Code reusability tools for programming mobile robots. In *2004 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*(IEEE Cat. No. 04CH37566) (Vol. 2, pp. 1820-1825). IEEE.

- [9] Lubars, M. D. (1986). Code reusability in the large versus code reusability in the small. ACM SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes, 11(1), 21-28.
- [10] Sadeghi, A. R., Davi, L., & Larsen, P. (2015, April). Securing legacy software against real-world code-reuse exploits: Utopia, alchemy, or possible future?. In Proceedings of the 10th ACM Symposium on Information, Computer and Communications Security (pp. 55-61).
- [11] Khapre, S., Singh, P., Shankar, A., Nayak, S. R., & Diwakar, M. (2023). Context-based intelligent recommendation by code reuse for smart decision support and cognitive adaptive systems. International Journal of Intelligent Unmanned Systems, 11(1), 75-87.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Autohers

Raoha Bin Mejba

raohamejba@gmail.com

School of Information Engineering

Sabbir Morshed Miazi

sabbirm2622@gmail.com

School of Information Engineering

University: Yangzhou University, Yangzhou, China

ASHIKUR RAHAMAN PALASH

rahamanpalash16@gmail.com

School of Software Engineering
Huaiyin Institute of Technology

Touhidur Rahman Sobuz

Touhidurrahmansobuz@gmail.com

School of Mechanical Engineering
Shandong University of Technology

Ranasinghe Arachchige Tharindu Harshana Ranasinghe

Harshana4789@gmail.com

School of Mechanical Engineering
Jiangsu University of Science and Technology